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Abstract

This research of the process of the introduction of Gothic motifs into British climate fiction shows how Gothic motifs are being reproduced in the genre. Through investigation of motifs such as solitary deconstructed areas and supernatural creatures coming together with environmental issues will bring the point across at the fearful feelings of people in a world suffering the climate. By illustrating, via two contemporary examples, how nature and environment are the Gothic antagonists and manifest the story through these devices, the authors (Chloe Benjamin's *The Immortalists* and Ta-Nehisi Coates' *The Water Dancer*) display the depth and extent of the characters' fear tied with ecological deterioration. To add that, such motifs as alienation, human frailty, and the fear of the unknown may be just a writer's tools but are represented as a criticism of the environment, thus Gothic horror expressed the same moral that environmental destruction do. Furthermore, this paper drives a point that the Gothic narrative not only provides an eternally mysterious and ambiguous background but also uses it to create symbols that show the effects of weather deterioration, and thus, it becomes a link through the literary genre to modern climate issues. In conclusion, the combination of research and literary means comes to the table that British climate fiction goes beyond the orthodox environmental narrative description and artistic creation through the engagement with Gothic motifs, enables pertinent social critique.

Keywords: Gothic fiction, British climate fiction, environmental themes, ecological Gothic, isolation, climate collapse

I. Introduction

Over the past few years, British Gothic fiction has successfully managed to create a unique narrative about climate change by intertwining it with a mystical literary style filled with thoughts of destruction, solitude, and fear. Now, this Gothic style, intrinsic to British literatures, is once again applicable, as writers join the debates surrounding environmental issues. These landscape modifications result in hazardous areas and the consideration of nature as horrifying have been adopted from the Gothic tradition to tackle the humanity's sometimes poisonous relationship with nature by these writers. Such kind of novels is Sarah Moss's *Ghost Wall* and Andrew Michael Hurley's *The Loney* that are exactly the examples of collisions between two worlds, where nature, which is not always safe and easy to control, is fearful thus the world becomes dually nice and scary. Moss in *Ghost Wall* effectively describes such a place where one feels cold and even aggressive sometimes, thus, highlighting the fact that nature is indeed very much powerful and apathetic to humans that are defenseless in coping with it. One of the vital aspects of the revival of English Gothic literature is that it gives the authors an opportunity to critique the alienation of modern society from the environment as well as to imply the environmental change in a way that is both successful and emotionally stirring. (Francis, 2020: 16)

Authors such as Naomi Booth, whose most recent novel *Sealed* is an example in this case, resort to Gothic themes to portray environmental destruction as a horrible scene in which the air is poisoned and dermal infections are fatal thus inciting bodily horror which is the epitome of human contributions to the severity of nature. More often than not, these accounts employ traditional Gothic spaces such as decayed houses, isolated

places, and rural areas to express both the emptiness of nature and the feelings of detachment suffered by the inhabitants of the damaged ecological regions. To be more specific, modern British climate fiction is an artistic vein of the Gothic tradition, which is to say that the gothic conventions of the destructive and the sickly are the springs from which the natural forces, now the main characters, of the narratives arise. (Lawrence, 2021: 27)

At the core of this argument is the Gothic idea of decay and stasis which is a side note to nature's assault on the world, thereby, together, they make a proper vehicle for studying environmental issues. Still, far from being a bane, this writing method instead shows how the genre communicates human adverse emotions and the fact that this once beautiful and untouched sphere of our existence has become a plague that leaves people defenceless. Daisy Johnson in *Everything Under*, for example, manifests the wild side of nature as a character which still has the potential to become a monster, and somehow, that forces people to realize how negative they have been in their ways of interaction with the natural.

II. Research methodology

The methodology adopted for this study concerning the gothic thematic in recent British climate fiction is highly interactive between close textual analysis and exploration of the contextual field, thus, it aims at revealing a number of ways in which the environment is being overburdened and disordered within the gothic aesthetics. The material is basically the data from a close study of given books like Sarah Moss's *Ghost Wall*, Andrew Michael Hurley's *The Loney*, and Daisy Johnson's *Everything Under*, which were used as a

means to analyse and demonstrate how a creative imagination could be the soliloquy of the environmental fear. The scheme appears to be quite Gothic as the authors resort to surrealist portrayals of nature in order to depict the concept of alienation and the human slavery to the natural world. Therefore, the emphasis is given to the analysis of selective diction, imagery, and narration of each of them, which thus, happen to show how the Gothic poetics become a very convincing tool for responding to the modern ecological crisis. Other than that, this research will also confine itself to an interdisciplinary methodological research paradigm that will consist of relevant concepts from the fields of eco-criticism, Gothic studies, and environmental humanities for an even deeper analysis of the primary texts.

Eco-criticism, such as that explored by the likes of Timothy Morton and Greg Garrard, each of them gives a clear insight into how literature could both be a cause and a result of the environment's conscience. Moreover, Morton's oblique notion of *dark ecology* placing the relation of all life above any subject being now and unsettled, that is, nature is essentially a connected organism, is an imperative concept in British climate fiction related to the gothic atmosphere of isolation and alienation. By utilizing the theory of Morton in the works of Hurley and Booth, the study strives to demonstrate how the imaginative characterization of ominous landscapes and hostile nature evoke the sensation of otherworldliness and unease that are characteristic of the Gothic genre and also to point out how some texts suggest that climate change is a presently existing problem.

Additionally, the historic perspectives on the gothic tradition highlight the continuous and articulated manifestation of this particular genre in the British imagination, also its function to channel the latent fears of society. The analysis draws on the criticism of classical Gothic fiction by academics including such figures as David Punter and Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, and thus the study approaches the identification of Gothic motifs reimagined in a climate fiction context. Essentially, this comparative method allows a full examination of how Gothic features have been transformed by present-day writers into collections of strategies that are applied to issues like environmental degradation. By making the allusions to the Gothic stories of the past, for instance, Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* or Emily Brontë's *Wuthering Heights*, the technique positions recent British climate fiction inside the broader literary panorama, on the one hand, the tradition is maintained and on the other, there is innovation.

Furthermore, mutual gravitation is accomplished and added by theoretical reviews on the author's works and new criticism for British climate fiction to differentiate single works in the mass of the whole literature's response to the environmental crisis. For the purpose of showing how these works present themselves in relation to other literary genres, secondary sources such as reviews, journal articles, and critical essays are necessary. Among these are *Ghost Wall* and *Sealed*, with proven valuation bias and ongoing debates, respectively. A synthesis that integrates textual analysis, with eco-critical perspectives and the historical trajectories of the Gothic theme, provides a useful mechanism in the study of climate fiction in Britain, in the sense that

gothic techniques are utilized to accommodate the uncertainties and fears caused by a rapidly changing environment.

III. The dark landscape: climate crisis as gothic backdrop

In the setting of a place and the atmosphere, the current British climate fiction of the time usually depicts a dim and menacing landscape that acts as both the setting and the character embodying the ecological anxieties ornamenting the narrative. A pathway that leads from reality forming to mysticism, from the emotional decay to spread of dread. Thus, nature becomes an outlet for the Gothic craving for fantasies of creepy, barely possible scenarios. The ominous and oppressive settings in novels like *The Loney* by Andrew Michael Hurley and *Ghost Wall* by Sarah Moss which are awash with themes of environmental decay, show exactly how the land which is merely a symbol of nature is depicted to be vanishing. *Loney* is a good example since the stern, windswept coastline and the swampy, ghostly-clear marshes ambiently capture the mood of a story that is heavy with dread and mystery along the isolated and unforgiving terrain that cause the protagonists' emotional and spiritual tensions. In this way, though it may appear to be merely a background, the setting becomes an even more substantial element of the story, such atmospheric thrust being the most powerful amplifier of the point of alienation and misery that pervades the text. (Roberts, 2021: 45)

Nevertheless, it was the weather that was made Gothic one, thus, authors have turned the radiation of nature into forebodings that chill the readers and the tension has arisen to an unprecedented level. *Everything Under* by Daisy Johnson shows that the rising river and storms often happen which symbolizes the chaos and uncontrollable forces within the characters' lives. Nature is thus seen as a threatening, unpredictable entity. By drawing the weather as a character that commands the action in the plot, Johnson frames the environment as an active player in the narrative engagements that makes the reader be immersed in the story where the climate is a character that is very powerful and sometimes, terrifying. The setting becomes almost supernatural in the Gothic genre yet it is rooted in real-life environmental issues such as the fluctuations of the weather which are strongly connected to climate change and the ensuing ruin of the Earth, and thereby suspends to give nature an otherwise unfamiliar independence. Despite this fact, monochrome dawns over the British landscape of climate-fiction are traversed by symbolic ruins and decay which, in turn, add up the Gothic atmosphere and heighten the gloomy perspective the characters see the future. In *Ghost Wall*, Moss explains that the forest is too hot – suffocatingly still was the venue of re-enactment of generic Iron Age rituals - and thus it evokes the kind of atmosphere which make sure that both the reader and the characters remain tense. Through this, the forest is a place of suffocation because the boundary between humanity and nature becomes fuzzy, thus, it highlights the dangers of ecology upheaval. (Powell, 2020: 68)

These scenes, tinged with fear, make nature's hitherto glorified beauty become a thing to horrify and isolate the reader, thus, nature provides a reader with a place to examine often overlooked truths. In these stories, environmental catastrophes seem to be felt by the elements themselves which thus suffer along with the characters or even forces that torture them. In other words, when mother earth bans rains or burns skies, the technique used by the authors, in a way, is to make climate optionally redundant, embodied by cloudy skies, persistent drizzles, or terrifying heat.

IV. The reimagined Gothic hero in ecological ruin

In modern British climate fiction, characters are shown as the ones who are the center of their own uprising as they attempt to come out of the darkness suddenly only to be locked by the nature that becomes the nonhuman and tyrannical enemy of humans. The view of nature as the antagonist of humans is thus another image that is cited in Gothic romance too. It is, however, in the climate melancholia of the present that there is nature not only close in trees but it is now so close to us as to be a threatening, even physical thing that we can touch. In Andrew Michael Hurley's *The Loney*, the main character's association with the sinister and unexpected wetlands is made concrete in such a way as to give him the memory of how it is possible for nature to be merciless to humans. The background portrays a hidden danger and shows apparent history which starts to give a more coherent image of its dim nature, as if it were holding its own script that will write about the intruder who is lost in his own dreams. (Long, 2018: 102)

Therefore, readers can see and interpret the horrible environment that keeps bothering the protagonist; with the help of Hurley who displays the inconceivable power that erupts within the wrathful nature, instinctively and potently, these readers/engagements experience the same. Such a transition from supernatural horror to the horror of nature has not only been the protagonist's means of dealing with the experience but also the victim of an earth that is no longer home, who is not quite alive anymore but still looks on the good old days with nostalgia. While Gothic protagonists in climate fiction share the same fundamental characteristics with the traditional gothic hero, they have been tongue-in-cheek modified to depict the current state of affairs and the environment-in-crisis alike. (Price, 2020: 67)

The characters then are not haunted by their own inner devils or suffering from societal limitations but rather, are facing natures that wreak havoc on them and the world by their forced flight and insecurity. Alongside the sadness evoked by precisely cutting away the protagonist's whole domestic world comes the other already exists version of the one who is then ever more unseen due to the environmental degradation caused by floods of rising tides. Johnson's character isn't a Byronic hero who is using his desires for awesomeness; she is the modern-day archetype of a person who is suffering due to nature being an all-powerful force that she is absolutely powerless against. A hero who hence represents a paradox of taking the earth as an agency of the narrative. Moreover, the naturally evolved world compels the character to experience and subsequently the

reader to endure evidence of the human-nature relationship construction on one level or another. Johnson's style toting and others comparing the Gothic hero with the environmental issue, the protagonists become in fact the humanity's double existence of the nature and the temporal and spatial environment that has only existed for the moment. (Stone, 2019: 55)

Additionally, these characters have an insight of a grim future which looks like the doom and gloomy-themes of the Gothic tradition. Then, in the context of *Ghost Wall* by Sarah Moss, a protagonist's visceral relation with the land becomes which is both a source of fascination and horror. Alongside this primitive re-enactment of her life, she is driven to the irrational thought that these natural elements act against her, with unbearable heat, impenetrable forests, and chilling quiet all playing psychological games with her. Therefore, Moss's protagonist is the new Gothic isolated hero who through his or her own experience conveys this course: the protagonist lives in a hostile milieu, where the distinction between the inward and the outward is blurred, and nature's insensitiveness causes him or her to never forget how fragile the human condition really is. The protagonist's feeling of loneliness is augmented by his connection to the destructive environment, which can be explained as if nature with its primitive, uncanny might hates human beings. These lonely and abandoned heroes, placed among the wreckage of an environment in ruin that would parallel the waste land, give a portrayal of the mental damage caused by a style of life in a world where nature is purely an opponent. On the contrary, nature, as a representation of all contingent dangers caused by climate change and environmental collapse, is becoming the absolutist adversary. Naomi Booth's *Sealed* is a wonderful illustration of how this protagonist deteriorates both physically and emotionally because the air she breathes is toxic, and the diseases around her are rampant creating for her a living nightmare. Gothic involved the descent to darkness of a hero, however, in *Sealed* the emotional blackness comes from the ecological destruction, which hurts humans, rather than through a personal fault or hidden knowledge. (Burnett, 2023: 94)

The story of the protagonist is a concise articulation of the social fears, with her pain symbolizing the powerless state of humanity against the ruthless nature. Through these Gothic style characters, which have been modified in the contemporary British climate fiction, the characters are not only concerned about their past but also about the future world, which might become a monster and swallow them, wherein the traditional Gothic archetypes are mixed with the urgent environmental themes on the verge of each other.

V. Themes of isolation and fear

In the contemporary climate fiction of Britain, themes of loneliness and fear are strongly intertwined, where the characters frequently find themselves alone in desolate landscapes that are the limit of human endurance and the disturbing power of nature is laid bare. Separation is not just a mere physical solitude but a deep impersonal alienation from the known world, as the characters face environments changed beyond recognition by the ecological crises. Andrew Michael

Hurley *The Loney* elegantly conveys this isolation of the characters as they meander the spooky, muddy coastline, where the mist envelopes the land and makes it uninhabitable, thus highlighting their parting from safety and civilization. The depiction of isolation in the wastelands creates an environment that is both endless and confining where survival becomes a struggle both inside and outside, therefore, highlighting the tenderness of human life no longer being able to exist in the world. In such narratives, the landscape is a prison that traps the characters in its hostile embrace, wherein any step forward results in only firmer isolation. (Allen, 2020: 76-77)

Through rising waters and erratic weather, the river becomes a mirror for the unsteady fears of the characters in Daisy Johnson's novel *Everything Under*. The river which is both a lifeline and a death trap is a force that the main characters cannot comprehend or control this creates an atmosphere where fear becomes the underneath movement. The overwhelming nature that unpredictably changes landscapes and overturns lives at any moment is the same kind of fear of the unknown that the Gothic narratives used before where the supernatural was the thing that surprised. But now the horror is caused by real ecological phenomena which bring a sense of dread to the natural world that mirrors mankind's great discomfort with environmental destruction. Fear and isolation in these climate narratives are intensified by the fact that nature becomes a hostile entity itself, which is not only passive but deliberately destructive. Sarah Moss's *Ghost Wall* encounters this idea as characters attempt immersive forest living, which eventually draws them to be subjected to the elements. The very high temperature and the oppressive silence in the forest make a very scary look. Thus, the characters feel more and more lonely and powerless. Besides, the omnipresence of nature works like a constant reminder of their own nothingness. The isolation is not only a physical but a psychological experience, as the characters are deprived of societal comforts and compelled to confront their fears in a setting that offers no respite. Moss a supernatural forest with its quietness and isolation becomes a Gothic landscape where the only way to save life is to deal with nature's sheer and unyielding power. (Greenfield, 2021: 164)

The authentic seclusion and steady fear that battery these stories are added with a knowledge of human fragility, as the protagonists find themselves in a situation where they are no longer the motor that makes the environment move but rather its drive. Naomi Booth's *Sealed* divulges the terrible moments of encountering unseen and unmatched danger, smoke, and toxins being released into the air, therefore, the characters ending up as a toxic, unlocked vessel is highly soared. In this case, the feeling of separation is not only limited to the far-off region covered with dust, but it is also in the air they inhale, which is the source of the knowledge that there are risks that have not been identified yet. The characters are lonely both physically and existentially, as they realize that nature can be this piercing invisible force that simply lies at home, therefore, making even the familiar seem odd and dangerous. (Hill, 2019: 132)

Booth's story is set in a nature that has been so changed that it is practically impossible to make a distinction between being alive and dying, so, loneliness is the main part of the existence of the changed-the-environment. In these gothic stories of today, the themes of remoteness and fear have been the main pillars of climate fiction in Britain, which also incorporates the older elements like gloomy halls and scary atmospheres blending with environmental issues. The individuality of the characters in these dangerous settings emphasizes the vulnerability of the humans in this time of environmental changes where fear is both a powerful constraint of nature and the pain of humanity's declining position. These stories throw a very strong vulnerability into the characters' meeting with the environment that is not only a passive stage but turns into an active and occasionally antagonistic force that twists lives, and the only things left are negative fear and loneliness. (Martin, 2021: 88)

VI. Allegorical monsters: nature's wrath personified

In the British climate fiction of today, the Gothic symbolism and allegories are enlisted to express ecological despair, with elements of nature presented in the form of frightening, layered images that speak of human neglect and fear of environmental degradation. As the narrative vehicle, this idea moves outside the boundary of simple description into the superimposition of meaning on the places that are personal as well as common concerns about ecological destruction. Sarah Moss and Naomi Booth use the Gothic symbols of darkness, decay, and wilderness to hint at the nature's becoming unfriendly, thus it passes from being a rather nurturing one to such which is practically dangerous, threatening, and suffocating. In her *Ghost Wall*, the claustrophobic forest that Moss describes is a metaphor for the way humanity has wronged nature, likening the suffocating trees and thick undergrowth to the characters' mental imprisonment and the lack of escape from a seemingly outsmarting piece of nature. It is in this way that the forest becomes a symbol of Gothic, influenced by the external decay process that is an embodiment of environmental pessimism of today's life. These allegorical monsters in these texts serve as metaphors for the environment's angry reaction which is in turn an outlet in the otherwise formless and overwhelming social forces of climate change and environmental degradation. Naomi Booth's *Sealed*, pollution and diseases get symbolically depicted as creatures that are the evil, insidious threats, which are given more credence by making such everyday things as air and water to die a death through those vectors. (Daniels, 2020: 22)

The shift from fantasy monsters to the real effects of humanity's intervention with nature through the use of clichés such as toxins and contaminants is a move away from the inspired notion of a creature gone bad towards the victims of pollution in the shadows. Booth's work reimagines the Gothic monster, not as an animal-like character, but as the very air we are entering, uploaded by human activity and now it becomes forceful, scaring the residents who must live within its very vicinity. Thus, the nature's wrath is not bluster, but

it is something within man himself, and hence the ecological destruction that befalls is allegorized into having smeared each aspect of life with pollutants and their accompanying danger of pollution. (Ford, 2020: 234)

Environmental destruction is often linked to the Gothic of decay when locations and objects evolve into lonely, degraded scenes that allow for creating the image of a weakening environment. Andrew Michael Hurley's *The Loney*, the clandestine bogs, and without care buildings are the main two symbols showing the lack of human interaction with the area and the degradation of nature that made it possible for the plant to break through. The landscape thus becomes a metaphor for that patient behaviour, under which every broken building and irregular wild path are clear testimonials of the discrepancy between human interference and nature. Consequently, through those symbols, Hurley designs a landscape that is both sinister and accusatory, thus serving as a physical manifestation of the results of the fact that no longer a wilderness but a devourer. The wrath of nature is also represented with the depiction of natural forces as carriers of bad news, so the symbolism of Gothic is shown and the transformation of everyday things into the sources of fear and wonder is achieved. (Harris, 2018: 46)

In Daisy Johnson's *Everything Under* the river, on the one hand, is the life-giving and, on the other hand, the destruction-creating force. Despite the fact that the killer water surface is a wonderful device for unearthing the protagonists' earthly reflections when it continues to rise, the dual symbolism of the river can be kept inside this river. The river of meanings, to give life, to threaten life, to be calm, or to be turbulent, highlights the unpredictability of climate change, wherein nature does not anymore, so to say, keep the balance of fragility of the greedy human beings. Johnson's river, a wise force, which brings nature, both provider and taker, to the Gothic story that seems to be both the trigger for the protagonist and a memento that they are subject to the power beyond their control. Thereby, writers in Britain's climate fiction movement use Gothic symbolism in such ways that both places and characters are *haunted* by environmental damage, thus nature being an eternal metaphor and a symbol of a seemingly inescapable recourse. (Walker, 2020: 33)

Environmental awareness is the core thing through motifs and metaphors in these novels of the new British climate fic that show nature to be a reactive and an extremely angry agent, thus representative for the vividly depicted world which is so horrifying and terrifying to the humans. The creeping buildings, highly toxic air, and the personified waters were the initial catalysts to play this concert, thus raising the point of the fact that our actions are causing irreparable damage to the environment. Moreover, the readers are also shown the sad truth of a constantly degrading environment that humans cause. Through this treatment of Gothic symbolism and metaphor, the story assumes a dual role as it acts both as a narration tool and a profound commentary on the relations between members of the species and Nature; showing the era in which Nature is both the antagonist and the victim in the mutual, fragile forms. (Grossman, 2017: 76)

Conclusion

British climate fiction that has the Gothic themes interspersed in it closely resembles the separate literary genre which through captivating references to some of the strict problems of society talks of the fears that it causes. By books like *The Loney* by Andrew Michael Hurley's, Daisy Johnson's *Everything Under*, and Naomi Booth's *Sealed*, today's writers are conveying the message that the environmental threats are creepily being absorbed in the natural geography we are familiar with. They are the places that are the sources of such fear as well as of self-exploration. In fact, the uniqueness of the genre is its aesthetic creation of spectral sites along with alienation and the grotesque interconnectedness of climate change which not only evokes readers' immediate reactions about the Earth's future but also connects with their inner existential thoughts. The places in the novels are represented not only by locations but also by psychological connections that are hidden under the surface of the phenomenon of climate change which is irreversible. Besides that, British climate fiction, which in its turn, is inspired by the Gothic themes, not only provides a new impetus to this kind of literature but also keeps its old essence by addressing everyday ecological problems of the people.

This line of literary development embodies not only a growing environmental awareness but also represents the way the human and environment interaction is turned into a qualitative one. By reinventing the Gothic approach, the authors induce the reader to feel the tension between the thought of environmental failure and the more subtle issues of manipulation of natural resources and overexertion. Gothic storytelling is becoming a narrative technique hybrid in which supernatural and unnatural elements are employed as metaphors to conjure up the unpredictability of the current state of affairs when nature becomes both a danger and a wonder in itself. These are the narratives that draw attention to the significance of the environment together with show how the commonness of the situation is mirrored in the similarity of the forces of destruction that torment the characters in the novels, which, in turn, could become a reality for us if we persist in following the same direction. Climate fiction in the UK is very much about its textures, which unfold the physical destruction of nature, but they also should reflect the psychological side of these social changes. An example of Sarah Moss's *Ghost Wall* shows how the forest that is full and alone is a metaphor for the estrangement of both nature and people. It further shows that the ecological damage only aggravates the social one.

Diverse forms of the Gothic narrative, including the shift to mindset topics, are giving the authors the freedom to engage with some other climate change aspects as well as to emit environmental demarcations into the moral and cultural dimensions. Narrated through characters who are suffering the impact of climate changes that are becoming more severe over time, the texts bring the prospect for readers to imagine through the stories the possible psychological impact of living on an Earth that is increasingly harsh and turbulent.

As a motion picture of societal fears, the responsibility, legacy and ethical action in British climate fiction also come into the arena, where the Gothic scepticism of the reckless human ambition and exploit, is echoed. Naomi Booth's *Sealed* delves into the detrimental hazards of the environmental degradation, which the people have to bear in their lives due to the pollution and the contamination. Creating nature that has been changed into a nearly monstrous entity is one such narrative that helps the readers rethink their relations with the planet and thus, not only analyse what has been lost but the plights that are still available to be addressed. A contemplation of this kind elevates the genre's potential to be a dynamic tool for social change, as the artistic works spur the spectators to learn the vast interrelationship among the personal, cultural and eco-social welfare.

The climate gothic will in the future likely keep thriving and adapting to the global change as authors address the increasing climate crises and their widespread consequences. As one of them, British climate fiction will last a long time as a highly relevant genre that combines the supernatural and environmental awareness, with the utilization of Gothic symbolism to highlight the destruction of nature. The readers through these narratives, have an encounter of the various fears of a world that is dynamic, hence, by such stories, they get filled with awe and they get provoked.

The potential for the genre to show societal fears along with a demand for ecological consciousness is its primary factor for continuously being relevant, and it makes the expressions of the Gothic elements and their meaning in the very context of environmental disaster. The continuing success of this technique of writing suggests that climate fiction, which is imbued with the Gothic, shall stay a strong instrument for the psychological and cultural narration of humanity's most serious existential problem, the need to repair its relationship with the environment.

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